

Switching to Emergency Remote Learning During the Coronavirus Pandemic: Challenges for Language Learners

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Received: 24 August 2021; Accepted: 15 February 2022; Published: 4 March 2022
<https://doi.org/10.46451/tc.20220104>

Abstract

In March 2020, the Cameroonian government decided to stop face-to-face classes because of the pandemic of COVID-19 and switch emergently to remote learning to slow down the propagation of the disease. This was a radical change in the way of teaching in Cameroon universities especially in public universities. This study explores the challenges of language learners in tertiary education towards this new way of learning. The method adopted for this paper is an online survey made up of 20 questions which analysed the format of classes and assessments, the challenges learners faced with questions on ICT tools they used during remote learning, access to and quality of internet connection and ways to overcome these challenges. The findings reveal that level 2 students of the bilingual department at the University of Yaounde I faced a lot of challenges during the emergency remote learning because of the coronavirus among which the lack of adequate tools to follow classes, very poor access to internet connection, difficulties in accessing the university website, or the absence of teacher/students live interactions. Some tentative solutions have been provided in this paper to solve these difficulties.

Keywords

Emergency remote learning, COVID-19, language learners, challenges, tertiary education

Introduction

Due to the serious threat of the COVID-19, Cameroon like many other countries around the world was obliged to move from the traditional classroom to online learning; this was certainly a great challenge for this lower-middle-income country (World Bank, 2021). All public higher institutions had to stop classes and lecturers were asked to put a soft version of their lectures on the university platform. With the fast spread of the virus whose effects (and treatment) then were still unknown; staff, faculty members, and students were advised to stay home and continue their activities online. This was definitely a new beginning for the majority as both educators and learners had never experienced this type of teaching/learning but were forced to transition rather quickly and do extraordinary things regarding course delivery, learning and assessment.

The term “distance learning” or “distance education” was first used in 1892 and it refers to a kind of learning where the learner is not always physically present. Tsai and Matchado (2002) say it involves interaction at a distance between instructor and learners and enables timely instructor reaction to learners. If in the past, it was used to refer to correspondence classes, it now has to do with online learning. Wrench (2020) draws a clear distinction between online learning and remote learning. This distinction can be seen in the Table 1 below.

Table 1
Online learning vs. Remote learning (Wrench, 2020)

	Online Learning	Remote Learning
Intent	Planned	Emergent, Crisis
Development Timeline	1 To 2 Years Prior	ASAP, Immediately
Instructional Development	Intentional & Guided	Haphazard & Emergent
Focus	Online Andragogy	Academic Attainment
Trainer Focus	Content and Andragogy	Content and Delivery
Andragogical Focus	Best Practice for Online	Best Practices for Crisis
Learner Focus	Engagement & Attainment	Attainment

Online learning is planned, prepared at least a year before with a clear specific objective. In online education, the learner works at his own time and pace but with a specific deadline. Learners may choose online at the same time adult learners who may want to gain extra skills or students applying for a certificate. Remote learning even though online too, happens mostly in case of an emergency or crisis. It tries to re-create the classroom environment as the student learns through the computer. Remote learning is done at very short notice with the student logging into a virtual classroom environment at specific times to view lectures or participate in group learning activities. Remote learning can be done using learning platforms like Google Meet, Microsoft Teams, Skype or Zoom essentially through moving content to an online space. As far as the challenges language learners face online, Kuama and Intharaksa (2016, p. 55) identified four major areas of challenges which are cognition, metacognition, technical anxiety, and learning styles and preferences. Talking about cognitive challenges, learners need higher cognitive ability to deal with the more multi-dimensional learning tasks and complex content. As far as metacognitive challenges are concerned, online learners need to monitor and self-regulate their learning by setting up a learning schedule to ensure they can complete all the lessons. The third challenge involves computer and Internet anxiety; computer anxiety has a significantly negative impact on learners' achievement. In terms of learning styles and preferences, in new learning environment students need time to adapt to some of the new challenges they will face.

Significance of the study

This topic is of crucial importance and needs special attention. Online learning is an emerging and new field still at its infant stage in Cameroon. Transitioning teaching from face-to-face learning to online learning is vital, not only at the level of higher education but also secondary and primary education. The Cameroonian system of education was not yet ready for this major step and the pandemic has proven that education cannot stand behind but most follow the path to development. While most studies have focused on the difficulties language learners face in learning a second (or third) language in traditional settings, very few works have been published to analyse these aspects online.

Objectives of the study

The objectives of this research endeavour are to:

1. Review the format of online classes and assessments
2. Identify the challenges faced by students of the bilingual department at the University of Yaounde I during the switch to remote learning because of the coronavirus pandemic
3. Provide some tentative solutions to overcome the different challenges

Research questions

In the light of the objectives of the study, the present study will address the following research questions:

1. How did their class online look like and how were they assessed?
2. What are the challenges students from the bilingual department of the University of Yaounde I faced during remote learning caused by the coronavirus pandemic?
3. What are the possible solutions to overcome the challenges faced by the students?

Methodology

This section presents an account of the method of collecting data and analysing them (2.1), the participants (2.2), data collection methods, and analysis procedures (2.3) employed to analyse the data.

Data collection method and analysis

To explore the challenges language learners faced to switch to remote learning during the pandemic, this current study employed a quantitative and qualitative approach. The researcher made use of a form-building tool, called Google forms. It is used as a platform to create an online questionnaire that is automatically hosted via a unique URL. This online questionnaire can be accessed for free through Google Drive. Google Drive is an integral part of every Google account, and it is best known as a cloud storage service and for its Google office suite. Google Forms is the ideal tool for this research. First, it is online, because of the pandemic it was difficult to submit a paper-based test. Second, it could touch more respondents than the researcher could personally meet. Last but not least, a software is provided in Google Forms that can easily help classify and analyse the data the researcher received through mail. Google Forms allows the researcher to choose among nine different types of questions like multiple-choice questions, short answers, paragraphs, checkboxes, drop-downs. For this research, we mainly used multiple-choice, checkboxes, and paragraph.

The online survey was made up of 20 questions divided into an introduction, two main parts and a conclusion. The introduction provided sociolinguistics and basic information on the informants that checked gender, age, school (department and level), nationality, first official language, and whether they live with parents (or family) or alone during the period COVID-19. The first part (quantitative) analyses the format of classes and assessments. The second part (quantitative) discusses the challenges learners faced with questions on ICT tools they used during remote learning, and access to and quality of internet connection. The questionnaire ends with a conclusion (qualitative) with open-ended questions where the informants had the opportunity to discuss their difficulties and give suggestions to improve this new way of learning.

The results of the questions will be presented in tables with percentages; each table will be followed by a brief description. A list of the challenges (and analysis) identified by the informants will be presented followed by possible solutions to overcome them.

Participants

The target population of the study included 217 Francophone and Anglophone students from 3 different nationalities; 207 Cameroonians, (95.3%), 9 Chadians (4.3%), and 1 Nigerian (0.4%) learning English and French (bilingual studies) at the University of Yaounde I (Cameroon) in the department of Bilingual letters who have been coping with the switch to remote learning during the COVID-19 pandemic. The respondents were informed about the objectives of the study and were ensured that all data obtained from them will be only used for academic

research. The survey was sent to the participants through their various WhatsApp class groups, through Facebook, and through e-mails (for those who had one) and they were requested to answer it only once. The results were exported using the associated spreadsheet from the researcher's Google Drive account.

Table 2
Information on the Respondents

Nationality			Gender		Age range				FOL		Level		Living with?	
Cam	Cha	Nig	M.	F.	15 to 18	19 to 22	23 to 26	> 26	Fr.	Eng.	Und-Grad	Post-Grad	Family	Alone
207	9	1	75	142	37	129	43	8	162	55	182	35	101	116
(95.3%)	(4.1%)	(0.4%)	(34.5%)	(65.4%)	(17.0%)	(59.4%)	(19.8%)	(3.6%)	(74.6%)	(25.3%)	(83.8%)	(16.1%)	(46.5%)	(53.4%)

The first part of the survey shows that 207 students in the survey were Cameroonians; 9, Chadians and 1, Nigerian; 75 were males and 142 females, 37 were aged 15 to 18, 129 were aged 19 to 22, 43 aged 23 to 26 and 8 above 26. 162 informants had French as their first official language while 55 had English as their first official language; 182 were undergraduates and 35 postgraduates. 101 (46.5%) out of 217 informants lived with family and 116 (53.4%) lived alone.

Theoretical Framework and Review of Related Literature

This section is an attempt to review theories concerned with learning online and the challenges of students associated with the switch to emergency remote learning in previous studies.

This study is based on the theories of distance education developed from leading scholars in the discipline, such as Holmberg, Wedemeyer, Moore and Peters (2006). Keegan (1996) and Saba (2003) quoted in Chaney (2006) classify theories of distance education into three groups:

- Theories of autonomy and independence: Wedemeyer considers “the independence of the student as the essence of distance education” (Keegan, 1986); the fundamental nature of distance education is “a distinct ‘non-traditional’ type of education,” which focuses on the independence of the student learner. Wedemeyer quoted in Simonson et al. (1999) set forth a system of distance education that includes ten characteristics that emphasise learner independence and the adoption of technology as a way of implementing it. According to Wedemeyer, the system should:
 - Be capable of operating any place where there are students---even only one student--- --whether or not there are teachers at the same place, at the same time;
 - Place greater responsibility for learning on the student;
 - Free faculty members from custodial-type duties so that more time can be given to truly educational tasks;
 - Offer students and adults wider choices (more opportunities) in courses, formats, and methodologies;
 - Use, as appropriate, all the teaching media and methods proven effective;
 - Mix and combine media and methods so that each subject or unit within a subject is taught in the best way known;
 - Cause the redesign and development of courses to fit into an articulated media program;
 - Preserve and enhance opportunities for adaptation to individual differences;
 - Evaluate student achievement simply, not by raising barriers regarding the place, rate, method, or sequence of student study; and

- Permit students to start, stop, and learn at their own pace.

Simonson et al. (1999) continue quoting Wedemeyer who proposed the separation of teaching from learning as a way to break education's "space-time barriers". He suggested six characteristics of independent study systems:

- The student and teacher are separated.
- The normal processes of teaching and learning are carried out in writing or through some other medium.
- Teaching is individualised.
- Learning takes place through the student's activity.
- Learning is made convenient for the student in the student's environment.
- The learner takes responsibility for the pace of learning, with the freedom to start and stop at any time.
- Theories of industrialisation are mainly interested in how the field functions and how it is organised. They incorporate the idea that distance education is an industrialised method of teaching and learning, which can reach a mass audience
- Theories of interaction and communication highlight the constructs of interaction and communication as important factors in distance education. They incorporate concepts by Holmberg, such as the idea of the centralised learner, student freedoms and independence, the concept of free access to learning opportunities and equity, mediated communication and deep learning, personal relationships, study pleasure and empathy between students and instructors, and the idea of serving conceptual learning and problem learning.

Ali (2020) examined how schools and higher education Institutes faced with the challenge of COVID can maintain continuity of teaching and learning while facing the threat of extended closures. He uses the exploratory research design that makes use of rigorous qualitative methods to synthesize existing qualitative studies to construct greater meaning through an interpretative process. His findings reveal that institutions that lack the necessary preparation and planning measures to face the rapid switch to online learning, need to put in place measures to avoid the excessive demands and tensions that come from adopting things quickly. He continues by saying that there is a clear need for post-secondary online learning expertise in this crisis and it should serve as a reminder that institutions need to cultivate this competency. All university entities need to work cooperatively to effectively launch online and distance learning. Curriculum and other logistics need to be considered and assessment tasks need to be revisited and replaced with assignments to avoid face-to-face final examinations. Acceptance and compliance by all stakeholders will minimise resistance and in turn, will facilitate the implementation of online and remote learning especially in times of calamity like the COVID-19 pandemic. Also, lecturers and teaching staff in general, are key stakeholders in the successful implementation of ICT integrated learning and reciprocally they need to be valued and assisted accordingly.

Khatoony and Nezhadmehr (2020) investigated the challenges that EFL teachers face toward the implementation of online teaching during Coronavirus pandemic conditions, particularly in Iran. In their findings, they discovered that Iranian EFL teachers preferred conducting online classes through the usage of technologies during the Coronavirus pandemic. They agree with other studies that online classrooms can be regarded as a useful alternative in difficult and unanticipated situations. Therefore, technology integration is perceived as the most direct and effective way to maximise the learning opportunity for EFL learners and minimise the learning problems.

Basilaia and Kvavadze (2020) discussed the capacities of their country (Georgia) and its population to continue the education process at the schools in the online form of distance learning. They reviewed the different available platforms and indicated the ones that were used by the support of the government, such as online portal, TV School and Microsoft teams for public schools and the alternatives like Zoom, Slack and Google Meet, EduPage platform that can be used for online education and live communication and gave examples of their usage. Based on the first-week statistics of the online teaching process at one of the private schools in Georgia, they concluded that the transition from the traditional to the online education systems at the school was successful. The system and the skills that were gained by the teachers, students, and school administration can be used in the post-pandemic period, in case of missing lessons or other similar special cases like the current one. The teachers have re-realised distance learning in a new way, have adapted the assignments to the new format of the lessons, which will be positively reflected on their qualifications. The online education format can be useful in the post-pandemic period, especially in the case of students with special needs.

Béch (2020) analysed the Cameroonian responses to COVID-19 in the education sector. He identified four main challenges the Cameroonian educational authorities found themselves facing at the onset of the pandemic which were (1) how to ensure continuity of formal education; (2) how to minimise exacerbation of already existing educational inequalities; (3) which tools to choose for ensuring continuity; and (4) how to enable pupils and students at exam stage to progress to the next level of their academic career. His findings reveal that the Cameroonian education system was not prepared for the shift from face-to-face to distance education. The approaches selected to ensure continuity of education (institutional, community, and individual initiatives, ranging from paper-based materials to distance learning platforms, TV and radio communication tools) showed some structural and pedagogical deficits. To solve these deficits, he recommends that the government integrates distance-learning technologies; and improves access to essential socio-educational services.

Alemnge (2018) examined the distribution and effectiveness of distance learning models in selected higher education institutions in Cameroon. He says the Ministry of Higher Education in Cameroon has contributed to the development of distance learning through several initiatives. His study investigates the learning programmes initiated in higher education as a result of the foregoing actions by the States to determine their modes of operation and to assess how effectively they are operating in the delivery of their programmes. His findings reveal that institutions of higher learning in Cameroon have adopted the Multi-media and the Tele-learning models as distance learning programmes. The telephone is principally used to support learning outside the face-to-face meetings, alongside email and learning or course management platforms for content delivery, communication, and assessment since computer-mediated communication, audio and video conferencing equipment seem to be either insufficient or absent. The study also highlights students' satisfaction and dissatisfaction. He concludes by saying that the programmes require current technology driving distance learning (equipment, structures, management, software, know-how and, trained human resources) to increase effectiveness.

Findings and Discussion

This section describes the format of online classes and assessments, the challenges faced by the students, and the possible solutions to overcome these challenges.

Format of online classes and assessments

On 18th March 2020, all schools were closed because of the pandemic in Cameroon. This section describes how students at the department of bilingual letters (University of Yaounde I) perceived the format of classes and assessments during COVID-19.

To the question, *What format/organisation was your class online (teaching-oriented)?* the students were asked to give the answer that best describes the format (or structure or organisation) of their online class during the remote period. Here are the answers from the respondents.

Table 3

Format of Classes Online (teaching-oriented)

What format was your class online?	Total number of respondents: 217	
	Answers	Percentage
	Lecturers downloaded their lessons (Word/PDF versions) on a platform chosen by the university	118 (54%)
	Alongside lessons downloaded on the university platform, some lecturers organised extra live sessions on Whatsapp, Telegram, Google, Zoom, Youtube, or any other interactive software	60 (28%)
	Some lecturers created their own platform for their courses like Google Classroom, Moodle	29 (13%)
	Some lecturers never showed up online	10 (5%)

This question describes the format of the online classes. As it can be seen in Table 3, lectures were downloaded by the teachers on the university platform. Alongside this, some lecturers organised other live sessions on interactive software. Others chose to add their courses on learning platforms like Moodle and some never showed up online for the class (some sent their courses in PDF and Word form to the class delegates who shared them with the class).

It should be noted, however, that students reported that conventional/normal classes were organised that lasted two weeks after online classes. Unfortunately, in the comment section, we observed that a good number of students were not informed on time and thus did not attend; just like some lecturers that did not show up for the same classes. The next question required to select the answer that described how their class looked like (student-oriented).

Table 4

Format of Classes Online (student-oriented)

What do/did your online classes look like (student-oriented)?	Total number of respondents: 217	
	Answers	Percentage
	I download every week the content uploaded by the teacher on the university platform and send back/upload my homework after reading	147 (68%)
	I participate in real time (live, synchronous) lessons on Telegram, Zoom, WhatsApp, etc.	44 (20%)
	I only receive materials to learn from and homework assignments through the class delegate (or some classmates), but the teacher does not teach in real time on the university website.	26 (12%)

This section aimed at understanding the participation of the informants during the online classes. It appears that the majority, 68%, downloaded the notes on the university platform after it was uploaded by the teachers while some participated in real time classes organised by some lecturers (20%) and a minority received materials only from their classmates (12%).

The informants were also asked to describe how they were assessed during remote learning. Their answers are reported in Table 5.

Table 5

Method of Assessments

How did your assessments look like?	Total number of respondents: 217	
	Answers	Percentage
Group work	167	(77%)
Assessment in class	26	(12%)
Weekly exercise	13	(6%)
Online test	6	(3%)
No test	5	(2%)

As it can be seen from Table 5, 77% of students affirm they were mostly assessed in the form of group work (that also counted as the final mark for continuous assessments), 12% say some assessments were done when school resumed for 2 weeks before the final year examinations, 6% report that assessments were done through exercises given and corrected every week, 3% talk of an online test (a programmed test at a specific date and time) and 2% report that some lecturers did not assess during remote learning.

The next question on this part checked the time each student spends per day on their online classes. The answers are grouped in the following table.

Table 6

Time Spent Daily on Online Classes

How much time were you spending per day on your online class?	Total number of respondents: 217	
	Answers	Percentage
Less than 30 minutes	33	(15.2%)
30-60 minutes	76	(35.0%)
60-90 minutes	38	(17.5%)
2 hours	40	(18.4%)
More than 2 hours	30	(13.8%)

As can be seen from Table 6, 15.2% of the informants spend less than 30 minutes per day, 35.0% spend 30 to 60min, 17.5% spend 60 to 90 minutes, 18.4% spend 2 hours, and 13.8% spend more than 2 hours per day.

The last question for this section reviewed the languages the informants mostly used with their classmates. As can be seen from Table 7, Francophones mostly use French when they chat with their classmates (75.9%), then they use Camfranglais (17.9%), English (4.9%), and mother tongues (0.9%). The case of the mother tongue was cited by Chadians who mostly interact among themselves, and using their mother tongue. Anglophones prefer to use Pidgin English (45.5%), French (30.9%), and lastly English (23.6%). This can be understood by the fact that at least 50% of the Anglophones in the bilingual department come from Francophone homes and are more used to French than English outside the classroom. In the discussion section, the

students complained of the fact that it was difficult ‘to remain bilingual online’ as they will automatically choose their first official language instead of the second. The reason they advance to justify this is that when they connect they do not have enough time in their internet bundle to communicate. So, they rapidly share and discuss what is important and the easiest and fastest way to do that is to use the language they are familiar with, instead of taking time to think before talking or using a dictionary to explain.

Table 7
Language(s) Used Among Classmates

What language did you mostly use online with your classmates?	Total number of respondents: 217	
	Answers	Percentage
French	123 (75.9%)	
Camfranglais	29 (17.9%)	
English	8 (4.9%)	
Other (Mother tongue)	2 (0.9%)	
Anglophones (n= 55)		
Pidgin English	25 (45.5%)	
French	17 (30.9%)	
English	13 (23.6%)	

The challenges faced by students

This section of our questionnaire identifies the challenges students faced during remote learning because of COVID-19. To achieve this, the students were asked first, to mention the technological devices they used to access their classes online, how they connected, and how was their connection. Then, the students were asked to draw a list of the problems they encountered and explain.

Table 8
Technological Devices Used to Access Classes During the Pandemic

Type of device	A smartphone	A laptop	A tablet	A desktop
	172 (79.3%)	33 (15.2%)	9 (4.1%)	3 (1.4%)
	217			

Considering the technological devices students possess during remote learning, Table 8 reveals that 79.3% of the students used a smartphone, 15.2% a laptop, 4.1 % a tablet, and 1.4% a desktop. We see that most of the respondents used their smartphones to connect.

Table 9
Type of Connection During the Pandemic

Type of connection	WIFI at home	Converted airtime to data every month	Converted airtime to data every week	Converted airtime to data everyday	When possible
	15 (6.9%)	33 (15.2%)	57 (26.2%)	98 (45.1%)	14 (6.4%)
	217				

Table 9 shows that the majority of the respondents (45.1%) converted airtime to data every day to connect for their online classes, 26.2% converted airtime to data every week, 15.2% every month, 6.9% had WIFI at home and 6.4% connected when they could.

Table 10

Access to the Internet During the Pandemic

Quality of connection	Good	Not stable	Very poor
	15 (6.9%)	171 (78.8%)	31 (14.4%)
	217		

Many informants complained about the poor quality of the internet. Table 10 reveals that 79% said their connection was not stable, 14%% reported it was very poor, and 7% said it was good. Students outlined several recurrent difficulties they faced during this period which are listed below.

Lack of adequate tools to follow classes (computer/android phone/tablet/applications like Office, Adobe, etc.) As we can see, the bulk used phones which is not the easiest way to have access and to read notes because the size can impede long reading and quality. In the comment section, some said they had to borrow smartphones or wait till some of their classmates had downloaded them to have access to them as they did not have all the required applications to do so. Some complained of lightning that will not only affect their eyes but also their memory. They still faced problems when they had to send in their assignments because typing on a small keyboard was a real challenge to them; consequently, some of them summarised their works so as not to have much to key in.

Very poor access to internet connection As it is seen in Table 10, the majority confessed they had to be up late at night or very early in the morning to go to the university website to download their lectures because their connection was not stable. For some, lack of funds made it difficult to freely connect as they wished. Some unfortunately could only connect when possible as it can be seen in Table 10, access to the internet was not very stable for most of the informants. For others, who had to leave Yaounde and go back to their various hometowns found in rural areas, the unavailability of the internet due to lack of and poor broadband internet was a serious threat to their learning. In rural areas, the internet is very scarce, it is a similar problem Béch (2020) reported in his study with several “unlucky” learners who were excluded from distance education.

Difficulties in accessing the university platform Students also complained of poor access to the university website. Even when the connection was good, the website seemed to be on maintenance as they complained that all would not connect for a class at a specific time.

Schedule for regular class Many students complained about scheduled classes. A timetable for regular classes was given which was not always respected by many lecturers. They would come to class but only a few lecturers will show up.

Social networks Many informants reported that they had difficulties concentrating on their lectures because of the various social networks they are part of. Since they could not more see and communicate regularly with their classmates, they often met on the various social platforms they were in when they connected to have their classes. Most of the time they will lose concentration when the connection is slow, or the class boring or an assignment difficult to go to Facebook; WhatsApp, Twitter, Instagram or any other social network.

Absence of teacher/students live interactions Not seeing the lecturer every time during learning was another challenge for students. They missed their face-to-face interactions. It was especially difficult as they had notions that they did not comprehend and could not ask questions to teachers. Unfortunately, many teachers were not available online and they had to wait for the resumption of classes to ask questions. Some teachers created online groups (kinds of tutorials) to discuss with students but not all of them could register on the platform and thus could not interact with teachers nor could be aware of exercises to be done.

Learning at home Learning at home was a serious challenge because of laziness (some talked of a sweeter and sound sleep when they had to read), the ambiance at home, noise, loss of attention, absence of a private space to read, lack of reading materials, and noisy neighbours. As seen in Table 2, 53.4% of the informants lived alone that is in students' hostels/*mini-cités* and 46.5% lived with the family, but overall, they all complained of similar difficulties while learning at home.

Ignorance of ICT tools Some students (especially undergraduates from Chad and a few from Cameroon) complained that they did not know how to use information and communication technology tools like android phones and computers. They found it very difficult to access, understand and use the university educational platform and other social networks that were used by some teachers for online interactive classes.

Anxiety for the future Few students say they were stressing for the academic year as they were not very sure they will make it to the next level because of the various challenges they faced during this period to understand their lessons.

Possible solutions to overcome these challenges

To overcome the difficulties language learners faced during this unprecedented situation, the government, teachers, students, but also parents must rethink the organisation of distance learning at the tertiary level. They should all build a solid teamwork to support online learners. Below are some recommendations.

To the government/university

- Equip students with appropriate IT tools
- Train teachers to the use of ICTs
- Improve on the quality of educational platforms (with courses that are well supported)
- Train computer engineers in pedagogy who can assist teachers in designing their courses
- Create a partnership with IAD (Internet Access Distributor) to permit every student to access the courses for free
- Develop online learning for student workers
-

To teachers

- Organise live and interactive online (video) sessions with students
- Create a forum for exchanges
- Motivate students and help them maintain focus
- Identify students who do not have equal access to technological devices or high-speed connections, or who are illiterate when it comes to the use of ICTs and support them
- Respect a similar framework when designing their course (with outline, objectives, exercises, etc.)
- Show more interest

- Think of a WhatsApp class as it is more accessible to many students
- Design a clear timetable for each course

To parents

- Supervise/coach their children when they are online, making sure they do not switch to social networks that distract them
- Provide sufficient data for connection

To students

- Stay motivated and keep interest through the courses
- Participate as much as possible in live online sessions (read your notes ahead of the live online class, ask questions and take down notes)
- Design your timetable and self-discipline yourself in maintaining your schedule and not allow any distractions to disrupt your plan
- Collaborate with fellow learners

Conclusion

Many studies have proven the importance and effectiveness of online and remote learning (Noesgaard & Ørngreen, 2015; Kuimova et al., 2016; Ali et al., 2018). It is a fact that with the global population growing so fast, a new hybrid model of education must emerge. The Cameroonian experience, unfortunately, was not planned and findings reveal that the move to online learning was extremely rapid. This resulted in a poor user experience for many learners, especially language learners in the University of Yaounde I. With very little preparation and no training on the part of teachers as well as students, results show that the students faced a lot of challenges. The pandemic has proven that a change in education is imperative; so, for (remote) online learning to be effective in Cameroon, there is an urgent need to think of a transition online and more importantly, to look for rapid solutions for its implementation.

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